

ANALYTICAL CHEMISTRY OF THORIUM. PART III. SEPARATION FROM CERITE EARTHS WITH *o*-TOLUIC ACID AND ACETYLSALICYLIC ACID

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From solutions just neutral to Congo red, *o*-toluic acid precipitates thorium quantitatively and also affords a method of separating the cerite earths, if the amount of the latter is not higher than ten-fold. The p_H of the liquid, which is not critical, falls between 3 and 4. Acetylsalicylic acid exhibits a similar behaviour, but the presence of ammonium acetate is necessary. When the $\text{ThO}_2 : \text{R}_2\text{O}_3$ ratio is not greater than 5, double precipitation is necessary. The p_H of the liquid in this case lies between 4 and 4.4. Both the reagents have been employed for the estimation of thorium in monazite.

In this communication the use of *o*-toluic acid and acetylsalicylic acid as reagents for the separation of thorium from cerite earths in monazite is described. The former of the reagents gives satisfactory separation in a single operation when $\text{ThO}_2 : \text{R}_2\text{O}_3$ is not over 10; thus it enables thorium in Indian monazite (when the ratio is 1.8) to be estimated in one operation. Acetylsalicylic acid does not precipitate thorium in the cold; precipitation begins on heating the solution and is complete only on the addition of ammonium acetate. In a way, precipitation of thorium by this reagent may be considered a "homogeneous process". The advantages of precipitation in a homogeneous solution have been discussed by Willard, Gordon and Vanselow (*Anal. Chem.*, 1949, 21, 1323.)

EXPERIMENTAL

Reagents.—The preparation of pure thorium nitrate as well as the cerite earth solution has been described in an earlier communication (Part I, this *Journal*, 1950, 27, 457). Both *o*-toluic acid and acetylsalicylic acid were obtained by recrystallising B. D. H. reagent grade chemicals several times until the melting points coincided with the theoretical values, 102° and 135° respectively.

o-Toluic Acid

Estimation.—The thorium solution is just neutralised to Congo red and diluted to 100 ml. The liquid is boiled and the thorium is precipitated by the addition of a boiling 0.5% solution of *o*-toluic acid. The white flocculent precipitate which results immediately settles quickly if the boiling is continued for two minutes. It is then set aside for 30 minutes, filtered through a 11 cm. Whatmann No. 41 filter paper, washed first with 0.05% *o*-toluic acid, finally with water and ignited wet. Table I shows the results obtained.

TABLE I

Estimation of thorium.

Expt. No	ThO ₂ taken.	ThO ₂ obtained.	Difference.
1	0.0748 g.	0.0749 g.	+0.1 mg.
2	0.1496	0.1496	0
3	0.2992	0.2993	+0.1
4	0.0374	0.0375	+0.1
5	0.0094	0.0093	-0.1

The smallest amount of ThO₂ that could be estimated by this procedure was 0.0094 g. A precipitate occurs even at lower concentration, i.e., 4 to 5 mg., but it is too small to handle with any ease.

Separation.—*o*-Toluic acid precipitates the cerite earths incompletely from solutions which are definitely alkaline. Advantage is therefore taken of this difference in behaviour, and the p_H of the solution is adjusted to the optimum value. Excellent separation is achieved in the p_H range 3-4 which is established finally when the thorium solution is made just neutral to Congo red. Thus, the procedure detailed for the estimation may be conveniently adopted for its separation from cerite earths. Table II gives the results of test separations.

TABLE II

Expt. No.	ThO ₂ taken.	Cerite earths added.	ThO ₂ found.	Difference.
1	0.1496 g.	0.09 g.	0.1497 g.	+0.1 mg.
2	"	0.18	0.1495	-0.1
3	"	0.36	0.1495	-0.1
4	"	0.72	0.1497	+0.1
5	"	1.44	0.1496	0
6	"	1.62	0.1497	+0.1

The ThO₂ is pure white in all cases.

Determination of Thorium in Monazite.—The decomposition of monazite has been described in an earlier communication (*loc. cit.*). The thorium in the extract, which has been freed from zirconium and phosphoric acid, has been estimated by the *o*-toluic acid method and compared with the values obtained with *m*-nitrobenzoic acid after double precipitation.

TABLE III

Expt. No.	Volume of monazite extract taken.	Th O ₂ estimated with	
		<i>o</i> -toluic acid.	<i>m</i> -nitrobenzoic acid.
1	10 ml.	0.1101 g.	0.1102 g.
2	10	0.1102	0.1102
3	20	0.2205	0.2205
4	20	0.2206	0.2205

Acetylsalicylic Acid

When a cold saturated solution of acetylsalicylic acid is added to a cold solution of thorium nitrate or chloride in the p_H range of 2.6 to 3.8, no precipitation takes place even after long standing. When the liquid is heated to boiling, gradual separation of the thorium salt occurs, and the thorium recovery is 97 to 98%. If, however, 10 ml. of a 5% ammonium acetate solution are added, precipitation of thorium is complete.

Procedure.—The following procedure is recommended both for the estimation of thorium and the separation of cerite earths therefrom. The slightly acid solution of thorium or thorium and cerite earths is neutralised to Congo red with careful addition of dilute ammonia and diluted to 100 ml. 10 ml. of 5% ammonium acetate are then added and the liquid is heated to boiling. To the boiling solution are then added with continuous stirring 50 ml. of 1% boiling acetylsalicylic acid. The boiling is continued for a minute after, and the liquid is set aside in a warm place. The precipitate settles rapidly. It is then filtered through a 11 cm. Whatmann No. 41 filter, washed with 0.05% acetylsalicylic acid in 0.05% ammonium acetate, partially dried, and ignited to the oxide.

When the cerite earth—thorium ratio is over 5, small quantities of the former are carried down with the thorium precipitate. These are, however, removed completely in a second precipitation. The thorium precipitate is dissolved in 1:1 nitric acid receiving the filtrate in the original beaker and the liquid is neutralised as before to Congo red. Precipitation with the reagent is repeated after the addition of ammonium acetate.

Under these conditions a p_H of 4.0 to 4.4 is established in the final liquid. Preliminary experiments have shown that below p_H 3.8 the precipitation of thorium by this reagent is not complete, while at about 4.8, the cerite earths also separate from the solution. Tables IV and V give some of the results obtained.

TABLE IV

Estimation of thorium with acetylsalicylic acid.

Expt. No.	ThO ₂ present.	ThO ₂ obtained.	Difference.
1	0.0573 g.	0.0572 g.	-0.1 mg.
2	0.1146	0.1146	0
3	0.2292	0.2293	+0.1

TABLE V

Separation of cerite earths from thorium.

Expt. No.	ThO ₂ taken.	Cerite earths added.	ThO ₂ obtained ^a .	Difference.
(a) Single precipitation.				
1	0.0573 g.	0.09 g.	0.0573 g.	0 mg.
2	0.0573	0.18	0.0572	-0.1
3	0.0573	0.27	0.0574	+0.1
4	0.0573	0.36	0.0581	+0.8

TABLE V (contd.)

Expt. No.	ThO ₂ taken.	Cerite earths added	ThO ₂ obtained*.	Difference
(b) Double precipitation.				
5	0.0573 g.	0.36 g	0.0574 g.	-0.1 mg.
6	0.0573	0.45	0.0574	+0.1
7	0.0573	0.90	0.0573	0

* Mean of two successive determinations.

Estimation of Thorium in Monazite.—Thorium in measured quantities of monazite extract (cf. *o*-toluic acid) was estimated by a double precipitation with the reagent. Table VI gives the results obtained.

TABLE VI

Expt. No.	Volume of monazite extract.	ThO ₂ found with	
		<i>m</i> -nitrobenzoic acid.	acetylsalicylic acid.
1	10 ml.	0.1102 g.	0.1103 g.
2	10	0.1102	0.1104
3	20	0.2204	0.2204
4	20	0.2204	0.2203

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